

LOWER CERVICAL SPINE INJURIES: LITERATURE REVIEW**Jan Dark Abu Ahmad,***6 th Year Medical student**Nicolae Testemitanu” State University of Medicine and Pharmacy***Pulbere Oleg Petru***Associate Professor***Abstract**

Aim of the Study: This thesis aims to conduct an extensive literature review on lower cervical spine injuries, exploring various aspects including etiology, classification, clinical manifestations, diagnostic approaches, and treatment options. By systematically analyzing existing research, the study seeks to enhance understanding of cervical spine injuries, contributing to improved diagnosis, management, and outcomes in clinical practice.

Keywords: Cervical Spine Injuries, Spinal Cord Injury, Diagnosis, Treatment, Clinical Manifestations, Prognosis, Rehabilitation, Imaging Modalities, Neurological Assessment.

Materials and Methods: A comprehensive search was conducted across multiple databases, including Google Scholar, PubMed, Embase, and institutional libraries, focusing on cervical spine injuries. The search criteria included full-text articles, reports, books, and book chapters published within the last decade to ensure the inclusion of recent research. Data synthesis encompassed prevalence rates, risk factors, clinical presentations, diagnostic modalities, and therapeutic interventions for cervical spine injuries.

Outcomes: The study underscores the significance of timely recognition and appropriate management of cervical spine injuries in optimizing patient outcomes. Long-term prognosis varies depending on factors such as the mechanism of injury, severity of spinal cord involvement, and effectiveness of interventions. Complications arising from untreated or inadequately managed cervical spine injuries, such as neurological deficits, chronic pain, and disability, can have profound implications on patients' quality of life and functional independence.

Clinical Manifestations and Implications: Cervical spine injuries present with diverse clinical manifestations, ranging from mild neck pain to complete spinal cord injury with tetraplegia. Understanding the spectrum of clinical presentations and their implications is crucial for accurate diagnosis and tailored management strategies. Complications associated with cervical spine injuries, including spinal cord compression, vertebral fractures, and instability, highlight the importance of prompt assessment and appropriate intervention to prevent long-term disability and neurological sequelae.

Diagnostic Approaches: The diagnostic process for cervical spine injuries involves a comprehensive evaluation encompassing clinical assessment, imaging studies, and neurological examination. Radiographic modalities such as X-rays, computed tomography (CT), and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) play pivotal roles in delineating the extent and severity of injury, guiding treatment decisions, and prognostication. Multidisciplinary collaboration among clinicians, radiologists, and neurosurgeons is essential for accurate diagnosis and optimal management of cervical spine injuries.

Interventions and Strategies: Treatment modalities for cervical spine injuries include conservative measures such as immobilization, analgesia, and physical therapy, as well as surgical interventions such as decompression, stabilization, and fusion. The selection of treatment depends on factors such as the type and severity of injury, presence of neurological deficits, and patient-specific considerations. Early mobilization, rehabilitation, and long-term follow-up are integral components of comprehensive care aimed at maximizing functional recovery and minimizing disability.

Conclusion: In conclusion, this abstract highlights the importance of understanding the etiology, clinical manifestations, diagnostic approaches, and treatment modalities of cervical spine injuries. By synthesizing current evidence and clinical practices, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of cervical spine injuries, facilitating improved diagnosis, management, and outcomes for affected individuals. Recognizing the complexity of cervical spine injuries and adopting a multidisciplinary approach are essential for optimizing patient care and enhancing long-term functional outcomes.

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